

ISOGAPP

International Students Symposium on Collaborative
Governance and Public Policy

Programme and Abstracts

Priming Governance For Global Political Dynamics Through Collaborative Governance and Public Policy

Makassar, Indonesia
23-24 July 2021

Organized by :

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CONFERENCE BOOK

International Students Symposium on Collaborative Governance and Public Policy

“Priming Governance For Global Political Dynamics Through
Collaborative Governance and Public Policy”

23-24 July 2021

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Contents

Conference Book	1
Contents	2
Message From Dean	3
Message From Head of Department	4
Message of Chairwoman	5
Speakers Profile	6
The Agenda	8
Abstracts of Parallel Presenter	10
Presentation Schedule	32
Board of Committee	40

Message From Dean

Faculty of Social and Political Sciences
Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia

Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh.

On Behalf of the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia, it is my pleasure to welcome all delegates from the various countries to the International Students Symposium on Collaborative Governance and Public Policy (ISOGAPP 2021).

Firstly, I would like to congratulate the HIMJIP as a Students Association in collaboration with Department of Government Studies, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia and Political Science Association of Kasetsart University (PSAKU), Thailand for hosting the International Students Symposium on Collaborative Governance and Public Policy (ISOGAPP 2021). It is both remarkable and commendable that the student association, department, and international association are hosting its international symposium to respond the latest situations. The theme of the international symposium, are indeed very timely.

We hope that this international symposium, will not only discuss some of these pertinent issues but also become a networking platform for both presenters and participants. This symposium will also be a conduit to promote HIMJIP, Department of Government Studies and PSAKU, Thailand as it strives to be an internationally recognized institution of research and publications.

Finally, I Would like to take this opportunity to express my deepest gratitude to the ISOGAPP 2021 Speakers, scientific and organizing committees for their efforts, dedication, and commitment to ensuring the success of this symposium. To all presenters and participants, I wish you all a fruitful deliberation. Let's open the International Students Symposium on Collaborative Governance and Public Policy (ISOGAPP 2021) by reciting **Basmalah** and congratulations to all.

Nashrun Minallah wa Fathun Qarib

Assalamu Alaikum Wr Wb

Dr. Hj. Ihyani Malik, S.Sos., M.Si
Dean of Faculty of Social and Political Sciences
Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia

Message From Head of Department

Department of Government Studies, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia

Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh.

This international student symposium is the first activity carried out by the Government Studies Program in collaboration with the Student Association of the Government Studies Department of Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar. So far, the annual routine activity that has been followed is the National level student symposium which is held and attended by all Government Studies Programs under the auspices of AIPPTM (Asosiasi Ilmu Pemerintahan Perguruan Tinggi Muhammadiyah) Indonesia.

This is something new and bold we did to support the realization of the vision of Government Studies Program, namely Excellence in Local Governance and Local Political Dynamics in the Southeast Asia. Some of the things that we will prepare among others are international joint research and annual international conferences. Alhamdulillah, now the dream comes true. Many parties have helped so that this symposium activity can be carried out. Thank you so much to the dean of social and political science faculty who has provided us for material and immaterial support, and also thank you to the whole big family of Government Studies, both lecturers, students and alumni who also continuously motivate the administrators to always be optimistic in holding this international student symposium. We also extend our infinite gratitude to all participants who have joined this special event, ISOGAPP (International Students Symposium on Collaborative Governance and Public Policy). We realize that there are many shortcomings in organizing this international student symposium which is being held for the first time, so on behalf of the Big Family of Government Studies Program, we apologize for the shortcomings in the implementation of this symposium from the beginning until the closing tomorrow.

Akhirul Kalam

Nasrun Minallah wa Fathun Karib

Wassalamu Alaikum Wr Wb

Message of Chairwoman

HIMJIP of Department of Government Studies
Faculty of Social and Political Sciences
Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia

Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh.

First of all let us pray praise and gratitude for the presence of Allah SWT because of his blessings and grace we still have time to carry out ISOGAPP activities and not forgetting also we send shalawat and greetings to our lord, namely his Messenger saw who has brought us from the dark world to the bright light nature.

There is no proper word other than the word thank you that I can say to the speakers and participants of ISOGAPP had been present at noon today, where this ISOGAPP activity is the first activity conducted by the association of government science students (HIMJIP) international level where this activity can make us establish friendship between each other. As well as understanding the issues that are developing in the middle of both in the region and internationally and also we can know what innovations and strategies should be implemented by the government. I hope this ISOGAPP activity can have a positive impact in the future. Once again I thank you as much as possible.

Wassalamualaikum warahmatullah wabarakatuh.

Speakers Profile

**Assoc. Prof. Riccardo Pelizzo, Ph.D
(Nazarbayev University, Kazakhstan)**

Assoc. Prof. Riccardo Pelizzo, Ph.D is an Associate Professor in the Graduate School of Public Policy at Nazarbayev University. Dr Pelizzo is an internationally recognized political development specialist. Dr Pelizzo's research focuses on issues of political development, institutional reform and institutional performance in developing countries. After designing measures and benchmarks for assessing parliaments' capacity and performance, he is currently devising several diagnostic tools to measure political stability and other dimensions of good governance. Dr Pelizzo is the Associate Editor of Politics and Policy. He is the recipient of several fellowships, scholarships, competitive grants and awards. In addition to editing 3 volumes, Dr Pelizzo has authored 7 monographs and more than 50 peer reviewed articles. His studies have appeared or been translated into 11 languages (Arabic, Bahasa, Chinese, English, French, German, Italian, Russian, Spanish, Kazakh and Vietnamese). In addition to keeping an active research agenda, he has engaged academic and non-academic audiences in 25 countries and has provided expert opinion to constitutional drafters, institutional reformers, and legislatures in developing countries from Africa, Asia and the Pacific region.

**Assoc. Prof. Srirath Gohwong, Ph.D
(Kasetsart University, Thailand)**

Srirath Gohwong, Ph.D is an Associate Professor at the Department of Political Science and Public Administration, Kasetsart University, Thailand. His research interests are on Environmental and Energy Governance and E-Government and published in many international journal and Book Chapter. He is currently the member of Political Science Association of Kasetsart University, Thailand. He is also the Editor of Journal of Contemporary Governance and Public Policy and Otoritas : Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan.

**Assoc. Prof. Abel Polese, Ph.D
(Tallin University, Estonia)**

Assoc. Prof. Abel Polese, Ph.D is a Senior Lecturer of Tallin University, Estonia and Editor in Chief of Studies of Transition States and Societies. He has been a Marie Curie Fellow at the Technical University of Dresden, Germany (2006-2008) and the University of Edinburgh, Scotland (2008-2011). In 2012-2013 he worked as a policy analyst for the European

Commission (DG Research). He has been a visiting professor to several universities in America (Harvard, Toronto, Manizales), Europe (Paris, Budapest, Dubrovnik, Moscow, Cagliari, Vilnius, Rijeka, Kyiv), Asia (Tezpur, JNU in Delhi, Konkpook in Daegu, Renmin in Beijing). So far, Abel has been awarded funding for over nearly €16 million and his project “Sustainable Development in Cultural Diversity” received the Global Education Award by the Council of Europe in 2011. He has also prepared studies and reports for, inter alia, the UNDP, the Irish Department of Justice, WAGGGS, Erasmus National Offices. He is the author of the Scopus diaries and the (il)logics of academic survival, which is a reflection on how to navigate academic careers, and regularly writes blog posts on the challenging of academia. Abel is co-editor of Studies of Transition States and Societies, a scopus-indexed open access journal and is active in debates and initiatives on open science and science excellence with the Global Young Academy, one of the main organisations dealing with science policies across five continents.

**Dr. Nuryanti Mustari, S.IP.,M.Si
(Universitas Muhammadiyah
Makassar, Indonesia)**

Dr. Nuryanti Mustari, S.IP., M.Si is an Assistant Professor at Government Studies Department, Social and Political Sciences Faculty, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia. Her research interests are on Public Policy, Political Economy and Social Statistics in the Governmental Issues and

published in many journals and Books, such as Mediteranian Journal of Social Sciences, Otoritas: Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan, and many more. She is assessor of provincial accreditation bodies - schools/madrasah 2011-2019 and internal quality assessor Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar 2016-2019. She is currently the Head of Government Studies Department, Social and Political Sciences Faculty, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar.

THE AGENDA INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR

“ Priming Government For Global Political Dynamics Through
Collaborative governance and Public Policy ”

Day/Date : Friday/July 23rd, 2021
The Place : Mini Hall Fisip Unismuh

No	Time	Agenda
1.	13.30 – 14.30	Opening the Agenda 1. Reciting Holy Qur’an 2. Singing of Indonesia Raya, Muhammadiyah Mars and HIMJIP Mars 3. Speech by the Chief of Association of Government Studies Department in Period 2020/2021 4. Welcome speech by the Head of Government Studies Department University of Muhammadiyah Makassar 5. Welcome speech by the Dean of Social and Political Science University of Muhammadiyah Makassar as well as opening the event 6. Reciting Prayer
	14.30 – 14.35	Anggaru Art and Paduppa Dance Performance
		Keynote Speakers
	14.35 – 15.05	Speaker 1: Dr. Nuryanti Mustari, S.IP., M.Si (Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia)
	15.05 – 15.40	Speaker 2: Assoc. Prof. Srirath Gohwong, Ph.D (Kasetsart University, Thailand)
	15.40 – 16.00	Time off for Pray
	16.00 – 16.20	4 Etnis Dance Performance
	16.20 – 16.50	Speaker 3: Assoc. Prof. Riccardo Pelizzo, Ph.D (Nazarbayev University, Kazakshtan)
	16.50 – 17.20	Question and Answer
	17.20 – end	Closing

THE AGENDA INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR

“ Priming Government For Global Political Dynamics Through
Collaborative governance and Public Policy ”

Day/Date : Saturday/July 24rd, 2021.

The Place : Mini Hall Fisip Unismuh

No	Time	Agenda
1	10.00 – 10.15	Registration
2	10.15 – 11.00	International guest lecturer by Assoc. Prof. Abel Polese, Ph.D
3	11.00 – 12.30	Parallel Session I + Question and Answer Session
4	12.30 – 13.00	Time off for Pray and Lunch
5	13.00 – 14.30	Parallel Session II + Question and Answer Session
6	14.30 – 16.00	Journal Presentation Assessment
7	18.00 – 19.00	Winner Announcement
8	19.00 – end	Closing

Policy Evaluation of Perda Number 11 Year 2012 Concerning Rural and Urban Land and Building Tax

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Various policies governing land and building tax rural and perkot aan in regulations number 11 in 2012. The success of a nation in national development is largely determined by the ability of the nation to be able to promote the welfare of the community, then in need of funds for financing development to achieve the goals d i want One of the efforts to achieve this goal is through taxes. Tax is a source of revenue that can provide a significant role and contribution through the provision of sources of funds for financing government expenditures . The role of taxes in development is very important, because the funds used to develop the Indonesian nation are mostly financed from tax revenues. Taxes have a role in the implementation of development because taxes are a source of state revenue for expenditures including development expenditures. The purpose of this study is to analyze the implementation of local regulations on land tax in rural and urban areas. To analyze the inhibiting factors in the implementation of rural and urban land tax policies. This research was centered in Gowa district, a location of several strategic agencies and offices in Gowa district. This research is centered in the district A location of several agencies and services that are quite strategic. The method of data collection is one aspect that plays a role in the smoothness and success of a study, namely observation and informants. Because the problem that occurs is that there are many people or taxpayers who do not have awareness in paying land and building taxes (PBB). So many taxpayers who have not paid PBB. Therefore, the local revenue office that collects taxes needs to implement or apply land and building tax management policies (PBB) in Gowa district. It is necessary to know what factors are the driving and inhibiting factors so that the community lacks in paying land and building taxes (PBB).

Keywords: Tax, Evaluation, Policy, Gowa.

Collaborative Governance in The Management of Horticultural Agriculture Sector in Rumbia Subdistric Jeneponto Distric

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The purpose of this research is to find out the form of collaborative governance in the management of horticultural agriculture sector in Rumbia District Jeneponto regency in improving the productivity of farmers. This type of research uses qualitative research with the type of phenomenonal study research. The results of this study showed three (3) indicators of Collaborative Governance in the Management of Horticultural Agriculture Sector in Rumbia District Kab. Jeneponto, namely: Making regulations related to the legal basis in holticulture agricultural activities through the formation of regional regulations. Furthermore, the function of coordination by involving the private sector and the community to cooperate so that holticulture agricultural management activities can run to the maximum. Then the last function of transparency where open access to information can be a solution to problem solving and program determination in agricultural activities. In the Private sector can be seen from three indicators, namely; Technology assistance where businesses have a responsibility to provide tools that can be utilized by farmers in agricultural activities. Furthermore, creating jobs management process of a company requires employees, where with the approach of empowering businesses to recruit the community so as to open jobs for the community and finally increase the human resources of businesses from the private sector always increase public knowledge through counseling activities as an effort to increase human resources capacity in agricultural management. The last one in the Community Sector can be seen from three indicators, namely; (1) Establish communication, in conveying all problems and needs of agricultural management to the local government and businesses and communities working as farmers are involved in communicating their problems in agriculture. (2) Participation, community involvement in the planning process, implementation until the evaluation stage. (3) Organizing, through the formation of farmer groups all the problems of farmers in the institution.

Keywords : Collaborative Governance and Horticulture

Women's Political Communication (dr. Karolin's Communication on Social Media)

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The involvement of women in politics consists of several sectors; 1) Women as the subject of voters who determine the vote acquisition in elections, 2) Women as actors of political strategy and 3) Women as members or legislative candidates in elections. Political communication using social media is one of the most effective ways to do this considering the progress of information technology is growing very rapidly. This study discusses political communication conducted by dr. Karolin who is on Instagram's social media account. The results of this study refer to Aristotle's theory, namely Communicative Ideology, Emotional Quality and Core Arguments. This research method uses qualitative research data that has been collected through Instagram social media and then processed through Nvivo, the data is matched with research that has determined indicators. The coding process is adjusted to the theory used. Classification of data as a process of retranslation of data coding, classification process using Nvivo cross tabulation, cross tabulation as a process of comparing each data. The last stage in the nvivo analysis process is the display of data in the form of graphs and tables, the analysis model in Nvivo is called the five-step analysis. So the results of this study that political communication dr. Karolin through social media Instagram gets 15% Communicative Ideology, 19% Emotional Quality and 65% Core Arguments.

Keywords : Political Communication, gender, social media

Alternative Education Services For Papua Natives (OAP) in West Papua Province in 2021

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Education is a basic right and must be fulfilled by the state. Lag in education is one of the major contributions to development failure. This study is about identifying education issues in the Province of West Papua and provides a number of policy recommendations for several parties to resolve them. . The parties targeted by this study are: The Ministry of VAT/Bappenas, the Ministry of Education and Culture, the Ministry of Home Affairs, the Provincial Government and the Regency/City Government in West Papua Province. This study uses a qualitasive approach which is a method that allows researchers to examine things in depth and detail. In this study there are two fundamental problems that make the acceleration of education development in the Land of Papua can not be carried out optimally. First, structural issues related to regulation, institutional governance, budgets, and educator programs

Keywords: Quality of Education in the land of Papua

Analysis of The Representative Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Democratizing Village Government

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The purpose of the formation of the Village's consultative agency is to provide guidance to community members on how they should behave or behave in accordance with their position in dealing with problems in society regarding community needs, maintaining community integrity, providing guidelines for the community to establish a social control system, meaning a community monitoring system for behavior. its members as a vehicle for democracy in the village, members of the BPD are elected from and by villagers who have met the requirements. While the leadership of BPD dipi li h from and by members of the BPD itself. This study aims to examine the function of the representation of the Village's consultative agency (BPD) in the democratization of the Padanglampe Village Government, Ma'rang District, Pangkep Regency. This study used a qualitative descriptive method and several informants, namely, the Village Head, BPD members, Village Apparatus and Village Community. One of the efforts towards a more advanced village, the BPD in Padanglampe Village always tries to understand the condition of the community and the Village Government tries to accommodate the aspirations of the community in accordance with the village authority.

Keywords : Village's consultative agency, Village Government

Sustainable Development Goals in Research Activities of the Education And Science System As An Integrative Component of the Global Cooperation Strategy

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This paper makes a focus on main tasks of implementation of Sustainable Development Goals in modern education system in Europe. It is revealed key area and better ways of such implementation. Philosophy of education has a special mission in creating of methodology of this activity. One of such tasks is achieved especially successful – to ensure equal access to all levels of education for all, including people with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children with disabilities. The anthropological method of consideration in pedagogy have to begin anew every time a new result of empirical research is obtained and it is necessary to ask what consequences follow from these data for the general understanding of human being. Philosophical anthropology is unable to provide a generalized concept of human being, and even formulates a position on the variability of ideas about human being depending on the type of society. Philosophical evaluation of the sustainable development goals should be the first task for the philosophy of education. It should be analyzed the correlation between basic values of the sustainable development and academic institutions, interrelation between state and private means of implementation of educational policy, based on sustainable development goals performance.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals, social anthropology, higher education, education system, social and environmental levels.

Implementation The Kendari Regional Disaster Management Agency (Bpbd) Function in Flood Disaster Management on The Wanggu River, Kendari City

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This research aims to find out and describe the implementation regional disaster Management Agency (BPBD) Kendari function in flood disaster management in the Wanggu River, Kendari. The research used a qualitative descriptive where data were collected using interviews, observation and documentation. Number Informants were ten people, and the data analysis technique consisted of data collection, data reduction, data presentation and conclusions/verification. The management of the Wanggu River flood disaster carried out by the Kendari City BPBD consists of 1) pre-disaster activities, 2) during a disaster (emergency response) and 3) post-disaster. The total indicators have been implemented quite effectively. Prevention and preparedness in pre-disaster have been carried out well. In the event of a disaster, all resources, equipment, logistics, and disaster management actions have been carried out properly, then in post-disaster, rehabilitation and reconstruction activities well done too. The Kendari local Government has also made various efforts to reduce the risk of flooding on the Wanggu River by building flood control retention from upstream to downstream, normalizing the river, improving drainage, and offering to relocate houses in the wilderness, which are currently still become problems.

Keywords: Disaster management, Flood, Function, Kendari.

Women and Politics in the Perspective of Feminism and Gender Equality in Indonesia: A Case in Makassar

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This study analyzes gender and politics which aims to eliminate discrimination between men and women, with a study on gender equality it will provide knowledge of the importance of women's ideas in decision making. The growing feminism movement can help Indonesian women to play an active role in the world of politics and become leaders who are usually only held by a man. The research method used is qualitative research with descriptive type. Sources of data used in this study is secondary data with data collection techniques using literature. Presentation of data in the form of brief descriptions and the like. Conclusions are drawn from the data obtained and then categorized and searched for themes. This study shows that politics gives women the freedom to enter and play an active role in the political sphere. Women who previously did not have the freedom to express themselves, finally gave rise to the feminism movement. From the point of view of feminism itself, women's politics in Makassar City has existed since the revolutionary period. At that time women began to get freedom and opportunities to move forward which gave a considerable influence in the life of the people of Makassar City. Women take an active role to help the community maintain independence by forming social organizations that are solely concerned with the course of politics. So, from the perspective of feminism and gender equality regarding the role of women in politics, there is already an opportunity given for women to occupy parliament as well as men.

Keywords: gender, politics, women

Good Tourism Governance of the Management "Beautiful Malino" In Gowa Regency

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Good tourism governance becomes a necessity for every local government as a destination for tourist to improve the regional order in an effort to advance sustainable tourism or as a producer of regional and local economies. The low management of good tourism, especially in the event of beautiful malino tourist destinations, is a thing that needs to be considered and it is the duty of the government to organize and manage the tourism area as best as possible. The lack of public awareness about participation is still very lacking so there needs to be monitoring from stakeholders or the government. The purpose of this study was to determine Good Tourism Governance in the Management of Beautiful Malino in Gowa Regency. The research method used is descriptive qualitative, namely an objective description of a program, and the type of research used is primary data sources and secondary data with 9 main informants. The results of the study showed several important indicators of Good Tourism Governance in Beautiful Malino Management in Gowa Regency, namely an indicator. Management that includes 5 parts, namely; (1) Planning to build facilities and facilities such as garden lights, public toilets, and pergola. (2) Organizations, involving internal organizations such as, Komunitas Peduli, Buluttana Indigenous Community, Malino PKK. (3) Implementation, all planning in terms of preparation of facilities and infrastructure and involvement of the stekholder shall be carried out properly. (4) Control, conducted to the Head of Tinggi Moncong, , the Private Party namely PT. Malino Highlans and Strawberry Farm. (5) Evaluation, still needs to be done because the problem every year is litter.

Keywords: Good Tourism, Good Governance, Beautiful Malino

Government Policy In Implementing Education Through Online Learning During Covid-19

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Since the government announced the first case of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19), the government through the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbud) had responded to the development of the spread of covid 19, by issuing Circular Letter Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Education policies in the Emergency Period for the Spread of Covid-19. This study aimed to find out the effectiveness of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study used an online library research method. The criteria for the selected sources were the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and online learning in schools. The results in the study showed that the application of online learning policies in schools was less effective because some of the parents did not have mobile devices (android) or computers to support online learning for their children. Not only that, another problem was the unpreparedness of teachers and students to the application of online learning. There were several things that could be recommended as a solution to the problem of ineffective learning during a pandemic, namely the need for curriculum adjustments during the Covid-19 pandemic, and the use of alternative facilities that were easily accessible by people in various regions.

Keywords: Policy, Online Learning, Covid-19

Government Policy In Implementing Restrictions on Community Activities to Control the Spread of COVID-19 in the city of Makassar.

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This study aims to determine government policies in implementing restrictions on community activities to control the spread of COVID-19 in the city of Makassar. The research method uses online library research methods, namely collecting data information by searching for data on relevant matters from various sources, such as documents, news and journals. The criteria for the selected sources are government policies in implementing restrictions on community activities to control the spread of COVID-19. The results of the study indicate that the implementation of policies for implementing operating hours that are spelled out in the implementation of Micro PPKM for MSMEs is still less effective, this can be seen from the response of MSME actors who strongly object to the implementation of operating hours which results in losses. for MSME actors, although its implementation has been able to reduce the spread of COVID 19 in Makassar City. There are two alternatives to overcome the issuance of the circular letter, namely: first, the government reviews and revises the circular letter and second, the government should prepare an online order application so that the buying and selling activities of street vendors can still be carried out.

Keywords: PPKM, Implementation Policy and Covid-19

Local Government Strategies In Managing Flood Disaster In Tompobulu District, Maros Regency

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Disaster is one of the risks to regional resilience, one of which is the flood disaster, which has an influence on the social, economic, and environmental community, necessitating the community's involvement in the government's efforts. The study's goal was to figure out the regional government's flood-prevention strategy in Tompobulu District, Maros Regency. This study is a qualitative descriptive study. Observation, interviews, and documentation are used to collect data. The Miles and Huberman data model is used by the researcher in the data analysis technique. The Chrysantin theory, which is based on formulation, implementation, and evaluation, was applied in this study. The study's findings demonstrate that the formulation or planning shows that the Regional Government has produced different plans, and that the Regional Government has carried out various types of planning or formulation, Specifically, the existence of Musrenbang, which includes discussions on flood disaster management, as well as other formulations or planning carried out by the Maros Regency Government's Climate Village Program, overcoming floods is divided into two categories: adaptation and mitigation. The intended implementation or execution has gone as anticipated, beginning with the construction of embankments, weirs, and low-rise streets, as well as demands for environmental cleaning, particularly along riverbanks and the planting of trees around springs. Evaluation of all types of planning, implementation of the evaluation section as a finishing or repair method.

Keywords: Regional Government Strategy, Flood Disaster Managemen

Public Policy Communication in the Implementation of Health Protocols at PKL GOR Sudiang in Makassar City

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During the current Covid-19 pandemic, almost all economic sectors in the region have been affected. Likewise with the trade sector which involves many economic sectors in the community, ranging from the hotel/lodging sector, culinary, handicrafts, transportation, and so on. Researchers have an interest in seeing this problem which the researcher summarizes in a research title "Communication of Public Policy in the Implementation of Health Protocols at PKL GOR Sudiang in Makassar City. Especially at this time, City Regency Governments throughout Indonesia, are instructed by the President of the Republic of Indonesia, to be able to optimize all potential, both human resources and budget costs in their respective regions to carry out priority scales in handling the spread and recovery of people affected by the Covid virus. -19. The research raised the theme of research related to Public Policy Communication in the Implementation of Health Protocols at PKL GOR Sudiang in Makassar City. This research

The results showed that the Sudiang GOR PKL Manager in tackling the covid-19 pandemic period formed a Covid-19 task force (SATGAS COVID-19) in the Sudiang GOR area. This is done so that communication and attention to all forms of information and communication about the development of the Covid-19 outbreak is centralized. While the Public Policy Communication Constraints in the Implementation of Health Protocols at PKL Sudiang GOR in Makassar City faced by PKL Managers there are 3 factors, namely: 1). Less than optimal communication, 2). Disorganized buyers, 3). The awareness of street vendors is still lacking.

Keywords: Public Policy Communication, Health Protocol, Covid-19

Strategies And Policies in Acceleration of Complete Systemic Land Registration (PTSL) in 2021 in The District of Selayar

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The formulation of the 2021 PTSL Policy specifically formulated strategic, sustainable, concrete steps that could stimulate the acceleration of the implementation of complete systematic land registration in Selayar Regency. In formulating the operational policy, the methodology used was the analysis of *strength-weakness-Opportunity-threat* (SWOT) in addition, it was also supported by desk studies, discussions (FGD) and seminars or workshops to get input from stakeholders. Increasing in implementation of these activities, namely through awareness and educated the public about the importance of the program complete a systematic land registration activities. Then the second effort was to coordinate with the Regional Government regarding the costs charged to the community for the implementation of PTSL, excluding the costs that had been set by the government. The third effort was to coordinate with the Regional Government on the existence of Income Tax (PPh) and Land and Building Rights Acquisition Fees (BPHTB) for people participating in the PTSL program, by eliminating PPh and BPHTB for people participating in the PTSL program. Acceleration of PTSL this specifically formulated strategic, concrete and sustainable steps that could be leveraged to achieve the implementation of Land Registration activities in Selayar Regency, so it had positive impact on the wider community. It was also hoped that the Regional Government would provide support and contributions both materially and immaterially.

Keywords : PTSL, Society, Selayar.

Towards Improved Flood Disaster Governance in Luwu Utara (Partnership Of Local Government And Private Sector)

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Regional autonomy provides a great opportunity to the region to develop or plan of regional development in accordance with the needs of the region, addressing the geographical North Luwu which is vulnerable to disasters, especially floods, then the planning to the reduction disaster should be understood and implemented by all parties, because disaster is not only the affairs of the government but rather a matter of all parties in the region and nationally Indonesia has passed a regulation on disaster management. The form of cooperation between the government and the private sector in the response to the floods in North Luwu Regency is a form of cooperation of mutual cooperation. The form of cooperation between government and society in disaster management in North Luwu Regency is mutual cooperation because cooperation is not there is a written agreement, the activities carried out by volunteering or without expecting anything in return, and regardless of the activity please help. Mutual cooperation between the government and the community to prevent and cope with disasters is very important to do. As well as in preventing and tackling the flood disaster, the form of cooperation that do not regardless of the mutual support and social work.

Keywords: Management flood disaster, Partnership local government and private sector

Implementation of Brigade Policy For Emergency Response For Natural Disaster Response in Bantaeng Regency

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The Disaster Preparedness Brigade in the emergency response in Bantaeng district as one of the policy products made by the Bantaeng district government aims to provide health services to the public quickly, precisely and efficiently. The research method used in this study is a qualitative descriptive method, which is to describe and fully describe the information obtained. The results showed that the implementation of policies from the theoretical approach of van Meter and van Horn implementation showed that the disaster alert Brigade aims to bring closer and accelerate health care to the community carried out by special and skilled task force who are on standby 24 hours a day. Natural conditions in Bantaeng Regency especially in terms of geography and topography, sometimes causing delays in handling health for the community, the Bantaeng district disaster preparedness Brigade has the main task of carrying out part of the duties of the health service and hospitals in the context of providing emergency health services or prehospital health care.

Keywords: Policy Implementation; Emergency Response; Disaster Alert Brigade

Resilience Of Hamlet-Based Smes in Bantaeng Regency During The Covid-19 Pandemic

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In the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic situation which has caused a decline in profits for SMES actors due to operational restrictions and reduced community activities, efforts are needed so that hamlet-based SMES actors in Bantaeng Regency can be resilient amid the Covid-19 pandemic. This study aims to determine the resilience of hamlet-based SMEs in Bantaeng Regency during the COVID-19 pandemic. This type of research uses descriptive qualitative. Sources of data in this study are primary data and secondary data. The number of informants in this study were 7 people. Data collection techniques using the method of observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis techniques are data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing, validation. Validation of the data used is source triangulation, technique triangulation and time triangulation. The results of this study explain the resilience of hamlet-based SMES actors in Bantaeng Regency during the Covid-19 pandemic which was carried out using Grotberg's (1999) theory, namely social support (I Have), personal strength (I Am), and the ability to do (I Can). . Hamlet-based SMES actors in Banteng Regency in order to be resilient by providing social support through the provision of business capital assistance, assistance and facilities that can facilitate SMES actors to become entrepreneurs. The personal strength possessed by SMES actors is a form of resilience through enthusiasm, confidence, a sense of responsibility and willingness to face existing conditions. Integrating social relations with good communication from various parties can be a marketing strategy for SMES players facing the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: SMEs, Resilience, Covid-19

Role of Village Government in Managing Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) in Bontorappo Village Tarowang Subdistrict Jeneponto

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This type of research is qualitative research. Aims to know and explain and know the supporting factors and inhibitions of the role of the Village government in managing Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) especially in Bontorappo Village, Tarowang District, Jeneponto Regency. This type of research is descriptive, data collection techniques using instruments in the form of interviews, observations and documents. While the informants in this study are the Village government, and the community that uses purposive sampling techniques. The results of this study showed that the Role of the Village Government in managing Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) in Bontorappo Village, Tarowang District, Jeneponto Regency. (1) Participation there are suggestions and inputs in the management of BUMDes as well as advice both managers and the community in the management of excellent BUMDes (2) Socialization contained in trainings per tri wulan that is able to improve the knowledge and capabilities of the community that has been very good. (3) Facilities contained in the aspects of facilities and infrastructure related to Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) are ineffective. (4) The supporting factors are the participation or participation of the community in utilizing BUMDes to improve the village economy. (5) The inhibitory factors that become obstacles to the role of the Village government in managing Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) as well as the unavailable facilities and infrastructure so as to impede the management of Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes)

Keywords: Managing Village, BUMdes, Village Government

Evaluation of Covid-19 Handling Policy Implementation in Gowa District

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This study aims to determine the results of the implementation of the Covid-19 Handling Policy in Gowa Regency. The research model that the author uses is descriptive qualitative. The instruments used in this study were observation, interviews and documentation to describe and explain the Evaluation of the Implementation of the Covid-19 Handling Policy in Gowa Regency. The triangulation in the validity of the data in this research is source triangulation, technical triangulation, and time triangulation. Informants in this study included a spokesperson for the Gowa Regency Covid-19 Task Force, Head of Surveillance and Immunization of the Gowa Regency Health Office, Head of the Regional Disaster Management Agency, and community leaders of Gowa Regency. The data obtained from the results of the study were reviewed using data reduction techniques, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of this study indicate the Evaluation of the Implementation of Covid-19 Handling Policies in Gowa Regency and cannot be separated from the 3 policy evaluation indicators that the author uses in this study, namely: 1) Effectiveness, with regard to whether a policy achieves results, meaning that the approach used is to measure the success of policies carried out by the Gowa Regency government in handling Covid-19 2) Efficiency, is related to the amount of effort needed to increase a certain level of effectiveness, this approach also measures the source of funds that must be spent by the Gowa Regency government in handling Covid-19 3) Responsiveness, what is meant is how quickly the government handles the Covid-19 pandemic and how the government makes an effective policy.

Keywords : Evaluation, Implementation, Policies for Handling Covid-19

Government Innovation in Eggplant Market Management Amid Covid 19 Pandemic in Makassar City

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This paper aims to see how the policies of the makassar city government, especially in the eggplant market in the face of the pandemic, especially in small and medium enterprises (MSMEs). Previously, the Covid 19 pandemic since it spread throughout the region, makassar city, especially in the terong market sector, experienced a big challenge for the government. The most felt impact by traders in the Eggplant Market is the decrease in revenue due to PSBB. The swordsmen are confused for their trade because of the difficulty of getting buyers during the pandemic, so their revenues dropped drastically. Around this economic issue with the rise of social and economic circumstances can be said to be very concerning. Especially complaints from traders who inevitably have to lose their jobs then the traders and the government are trying to provide solutions for traders affected by the pandemic. And finally traders in the eggplant market take advantage of the development of technology in the process of trading or in other words online sales.

Keywords: Government, Traders, Pandemic.

Disparity of Central and Local Government Policies in Tackling The Impact of Covid-19 on The People of Makassar City

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Disparity (disparity; dis-parity) is basically a concept, namely parity (parity), which means that the number or value of the parity concept itself can not be separated from the principle of proportionality and this becomes one unit (Ardiansyah, 14 July 2017). And according to the KBBI, disparity is a difference. Therefore, policy disparity can be said that there are differences or inequalities in a policy that will be implemented, namely between central and regional government policies in the case of Covid-19 in the city of Makassar. The results show that disparity should not occur in the policies of the central and local governments because it will cause an imbalance, therefore regional autonomy is born which discusses decentralization and the relationship between central and local governments. In this study, Edward III identifies aspects that are strongly suspected to support the implementation of policies, namely: communication, resources, disposition or implementers and coordination both at home and abroad. Therefore, there will be no policy disparity if these 4 aspects and internal and external coordination are used in carrying out policies related to overcoming the impact of COVID-19 on the people of Makassar

Keywords: Policy disparities, Regional Autonomy, Covid-19

Implementation of Electronic Money (E-Money) Policy at The Tollgate Reform of Makassar City

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The purpose of this study was to find out the implementation of the Policy on the Use of Electronic Money (E-Money) at the Makassar City Reform Toll Gate. The number of informants in this study were 04 people. This study used qualitative research with a phenomenological type of research that emphasized the subjectivity of human life experience. Data collection techniques used the method of observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis used interactive analysis model. The results showed that the implementation of the Use Policy Electronic Money (e-money) at Toll Gate Reform Makassar City had not been fully implemented optimally it was seen from the indicators (1) input, use of the system E-Money Toll was still less than the maximum (2) process, there were still people who made manual payments because the lack of socialization on the use of E-Money tolls. (3) output, some communities had not used (4) benefits, did not harm people's time and (5) outcome was less comprehensive in the use of E-Money Toll.

Keywords: Implementation, E-Money Toll, Makassar City

Internal Youth, Sports and Tourism Department Strategies Developing Lewaja Natural Bath Tourism Objects in Enrekang District

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Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism in Developing Natural Bathing Attractions Lewaja in Enrekang Regency. The type of research used in this research is qualitative descriptive research method using phenomenological approach. Data collection is done through observations, interviews and documentation. Informants in this study are the secretary of the youth sports and tourism office of Enrekang Regency, the field of finance dispopar, the field of facilities and tourism kasi as the person in charge of natural bathing tourism lewaja and visitors. Data analysis techniques used in research are source triangulation, engineering triangulation and time triangulation. The results showed that the development of natural bathing attractions lewaja required an important role of human resources that carry out development activities. The development process conducts training and education by building partners by presenting presenters who have knowledge about tourism. The budget reached Rp. 130,000,000 from the total budget of Rp. 170,000,000 from the total prepared in 2020. The remaining funds will continue to be maximized until the end of 2020. The rides provided today are swimming pools and waterfalls of lewaja natural baths only need to pay attention to the quality of water and maintain the lack of facilities and the need for the addition of waahana. By regulation the application is not so binding on visitors and is flexible still have to pay attention to the safety of visitors.

Keywords: Strategy, Development, Tourism

Implementation of Good Environmental Governance in Waterfront City Development in Majene District

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This article discusses the application of good environmental governance in waterfront city development. The title raised as described above is based on the problems faced, namely "how the application of the principles of good environmental governance in waterfront city development in Majene district". The method used in this study is a qualitative descriptive approach. Informants in this study were 5 people. Data collection, techniques in this study were observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of this study have been effective and it can be concluded that (1) the application of good environmental governance in waterfront city development in the regency of majene, includes five principles of good environmental governance in waterfront city development, namely, (a) community empowerment (b) transparency (c) consistent (d) clarity (e) law enforcement. (2) As for the supporting factors in waterfront city development are the government and society while the inhibiting factor is the availability of material and community participation.

Keywords : Good Environmental Governance, Development, Waterfront City

Effect of Online Learning Policy in The Era of Covid-19 on The Quality of Students of State 8 Small Bulukumba in Bulukumba District

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This study aims to analyze the effect of online learning policies in the Covid-19 era on the quality of students at SMA Negeri 8 Bulukumba. The type of research used in this research is a combination method (mixed method), namely quantitative and qualitative with instruments in the form of questionnaires and interviews. Determination of the sample in this study using probability sampling technique, the categories are students of SMA Negeri 8 Bulukumba and the number of samples taken in this study were 90 people and 5 informants. Data collection techniques used are observation, questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used regression analysis. The validity of the data was obtained through validity and reliability tests. The results of this study indicate that the influence of online learning policies in the Covid-19 era on the quality of students at SMA Negeri 8 Bulukumba is going very well. This is based on the average score obtained from the statement items of 346 or 63.2% which indicates that the implementation of online learning has a positive and significant effect on the quality of students. Then there are 30% and 5.27% disagree due to student interest in the online learning process.

Keywords: Policy, Online Learning, Covid-19 Era, Student Quality.

Helping Communities Facing Social Changes as Impact of Covid-19

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The purpose of this study was to find out the government's strategy in dealing with social changes as a result of Covid-19 in the Benteng District, Selayar Islands Regency. The research method used is a qualitative description, which describes the state of the object in the present qualitatively the data obtained from the research. Sources of data used are primary data sources and secondary data with the number of informants 6 people. Data collection techniques using the method of observation, interviews and documentation. The analysis technique used is data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing. The results of the study show that (1) Socialization and Education are strategies in an effort to increase public awareness or understanding of Covid-19 and actions in dealing with the impact of Covid-19 so that people can easily adapt to the environment (2) Search, Inspection and treatment is an effort The government of the Benteng sub-district government together with the Puskesmas to review in the field whether there are new cases, meet the needs of Covid-19 patients, and provide moral support to control anxiety. (3) Opening the Covid-19 Command Post in Benteng Sub-district, which is a facility provided by the sub-district government to the community to get a more detailed and clear explanation (4). the quality of learning is to divide the bold learning method into 2, namely brave (in the network) and captivating (outside the network) with several conditions. There are various social changes in society due to Covid-19, which in general are social interactions and people are more concerned with health

Keywords: Government Strategy, Social Change, Covid-19

The Influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance in The Scope of Government in The Kelurahan Office Samata Somba Opu District, Gowa Regency

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This study aims to determine respondents' responses to the influence of leadership style on employee performance within the scope of government at the Samata Village Office, Sombaopu District, Gowa Regency. The type of research used is quantitative research with descriptive research type. The sampling technique used is saturated sampling with measurement of research instruments, namely; likert's scale. The data analysis techniques used are descriptive statistical analysis techniques and simple regression analysis techniques with the help of the SPSS version 26 software application. The results of the research with descriptive statistical analysis obtained the results of respondents' responses of 86.56% which showed that the leadership style in the assessment was very good and the responses were very good. respondents regarding employee performance obtained results of 87.12% which showed that the performance of employees at the Samata Village Office was classified as very good. The results of the regression equation can be interpreted based on the t value, it is known that the t value is $29,860 > t$ table $2,160$, so it can be concluded that the leadership style variable (X) affects the performance of employees (Y) in the scope of government at the Samata Output Office, Sombaopu District, Gowa Regency.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Employee Performance, Scope of Government

The Pandemic and the Decline of Indonesian Democracy: The Snare of Patronage and Clientelism of Local Democracy

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The quality of Indonesia's democracy has decreased, and several findings of democratic institutions indicate a significant reduction that touches aspects of civil liberties and pluralism and the function of government. The method used in this research is qualitative with a meta-theory approach. The results of this study show, first, over the past year, the political and democratic sectors, especially in the context of general elections, are still at high risk of corruption. Corruption in Indonesia is political corruption which is the mother of all forms of corruption in the state structure that can affect the implementation process and the quality of democracy. Second, requests for political dowries by political parties and corruption by regional heads for campaigning purposes. They resulted in interactions between elites that form patronage and clientelism composed of patrons held by the economic elite with resources. The two factors above are important reasons for the estimation of the declining quality of Indonesian democracy.

Keywords: Decline Democracy, Patronage, Clientelism, Local Democracy, Indonesia

International Students Symposium on Collaborative Governance and Public Policy

The Effect of Village Expansion on Public Development and Services in Wonorejo Timur Village, Mangkutana District, Luwu Timur Regency

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This study aims to determine the effect of the village expansion policy on aspects of development and public services in Wonorejo village, Mangkutana district, Luwu Timur district. In order to achieve this goal, the researchers used data collection techniques through interviews, observations and documentation. The data obtained from the research results were then processed using qualitative analysis to determine the effect of the village expansion policy on aspects of development and public services in Wonorejo Village, Mangkutana District, Luwu Timur Regency. The results showed that the influence of the village expansion policy on aspects of development and public services in Wonorejo Village, Mangkutana District, Luwu Timur Regency had a positive influence on development and public services there, especially on the development of village markets, revitalization of village offices, mosques, and on service aspects. namely the birth certificate and family card services which are seen from several indicators namely, system/procedure, service period, costs/tariffs, facilities and infrastructure and competence of implementers. According to the results of the study, the expansion that occurred in Wonorejo Village, Mangkutana District, Luwu Timur Regency, had a very positive effect on development and public services there, because it brought better changes when compared to before the expansion. In other words, the expansion of Wonorejo village has fulfilled the expectations of all Wonorejo villagers who want a development and quality service.

Keywords : Village Expansion, Development, Public Service

The Role of Modern Concepts of Social Transformation of Education in The Institutional Provision of Sustainable Development Strategies

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In the current trends of the strategy of sustainable social development in general, and the education system in particular, there is an increasing need to solve in theory and practice the problem of civic institutional democratization, in particular, education systems and education governance and implementation of the idea of democratic social upbringing and education. The need to discuss this problem is due to a set of reasons. The most important of them is the direction of modern changes in society and education. Democratization of the system of institutions of society and systems of upbringing and education is a key task in many countries and involves not only the decentralization of education at the state level, but also the humanization of relations, democratization of governance at all levels of the system. The slogans of democratization were also proclaimed in Ukraine at the first stage of educational reform, but so far, they have not been fully transformed into educational practice. Moreover, difficulties in implementing democratic slogans have led to the slowdown and frustration of democratization, and sometimes to a conservative reaction. Democratization has been particularly difficult at the level of educational institutions.

Keywords: institutional democratization, social transformation, philosophy of education, critical pedagogy, globalization

Disaster Management Concepts Based on Public Policy Perspective

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Disaster mitigation is an early session of disaster management that is more towards reducing disaster risk for disaster-prone areas as an effort to minimize the higher risks caused by natural disasters. The purpose of this research is to discuss disaster management policies in disaster-prone areas based on the National Long-Term Development Plan (RPJPN) 2005-2025. descriptive method is used to clarify the reflection of disaster-prone areas mitigation based on theoretical in-depth analysis and comparative secondary information documents from the RPJPN. The results of the research show, conceptual model of disaster mitigation as output, empirical condition of disaster-prone areas as input, executive and legislative processes as stages in the public policy period. Not only that, disaster management is included in the policy plan in the RPJPN through the development strategy of disaster protection and preparedness as an effort to maximize the capacity of the government in each region when experiencing natural disasters.

Keywords: Disaster Management, Public Policy

Governance Land Ownership in Makassar City: an Analysis of the Political Struggle of the Urban Poor in BaraBarayya Makassar City

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Introduction state the theme of the article, research background and problem statement. Objectives state the objectives of the study, objectives. Methodology / Approach - specify the research method, sampling and data collection. Findings - study results and interpretation of results. Please indicate the main results and conclusions. Originality / Value / Implication - states the importance of research, novelty. Abstracts can be written in English or Indonesian with single spaces. Usually it must exceed 200 - 250 words, justified.

Keywords: Public Struggle, Urban Poor, FORWA (Forum Warga)

Role of Bappeda in Regional Development to Know the Implementation of Tasks and Functions in Gorontalo

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Regional development as an integral part of national development cannot be separated from the principle of regional autonomy. As an autonomous region, the region has the authority and responsibility to carry out the interests of the community based on the principles of openness, community participation, and accountability to the community. To support the implementation of regional autonomy, it is necessary to have broad, real, and responsible authority in the regions in a proportional and fair manner, away from practices of corruption, collusion, and nepotism and a balance between central and regional government finances. In view of this, one of the government's efforts in order to advance development in the region is to establish an agency specifically tasked with development planning, namely through Presidential Decree no. 27 of 1980, concerning the establishment of the Regional Development Planning Agency, which is abbreviated as BAPPEDA in Level I Regions and Level II Regions (now provincial and district/city regions) throughout the country which was later merged with PP RI No. 41 of 2007 concerning Regional Apparatus Organizations, The fourth part of article 6 concerning the Regional Development Planning Agency, to achieve this, the performance of government officials is needed.

Keywords: Regional Development, Implementation of Tasks, Functions

Gender and Politics : Involvement of Women in Political Development

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Gender issue is an issue that demands social and cultural construction justice between men and women. In the demands of this construction, it is hoped that the balance of function, status, and nature between the sexes can be realized. On the other hand, development is a construction of changes that occur in society from certain socio-cultural conditions towards something that is considered more valuable. In addition, it can also be interpreted as an effort to eradicate underdevelopment. Therefore, gender and development are a reciprocal correlation with each other. The emergence of the issue of gender inequality or gender discrimination due to the process of social construction in society. In fact, Islam and the constitution of 45 countries have guaranteed equal access for women and men. Therefore, increasing the role of women and men in gender-oriented development as an integral part of national development, has an important meaning in efforts to realize harmonious partnerships between men and women or realize gender equality and justice in various fields. life and development. The results of this study, trying to show that gender in development does not have to be equal in roles between men and women, there are areas that can be done by men and women.

Keywords: Gender, Political Development

Smart Governance Program Jeneponto Gammara as A City Brand in Jeneponto District

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The type of research used is qualitative with the type of research using a case study approach where data can be obtained from all parties concerned, either through interviews, observation, and documentation. Where the data source is obtained from primary data through interviews and direct observation and secondary data obtained through documentation and supporting documents. The informants involved in this study amounted to 9 people consisting of the Sanitation Service, BAPPEDA, Pancasila Ormas and the Community in Jeneponto Regency. Data collection techniques were carried out through observation, interviews and documentation. As well as analysis through data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions. By measuring the validity of the data through source triangulation, technical triangulation and time triangulation. The results of this study show three (3) indicators in viewing the Jeneponto Gammara Smart Governance Program as a City Brand in Jeneponto Regency, namely: first, citizen participation, community involvement through the construction of a waste bank in maintaining cleanliness, community creativity in recycling waste into something of economic value and beautiful thing is through socialization and counseling conducted by the government of Jeneponto Regency. secondly, information disclosure, an information technology approach that is a means for the Jeneponto Regency government to create transparent services that make it easier for the public to access all the information needed so that the public can access it without being constrained by space and time.

Keywords: Smart Governance, City Brand and Jeneponto Gammara

Client Patron Pattern on East Kolaka Regional Head of Election 2015 (Case in Lalingato Village, Tirawuta District, East Kolaka)

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Regional head elections are a vehicle for the society to elect regional heads directly and held honestly, fairly, and safely. The 2015 regional head elections in East Kolaka approached the village head to get votes. The pattern of the relationship is a patron-client relationship where the candidate for regent is the patron (someone who has power, authority, and influence and the village head is the client (someone who provides loyalty in the form of vote support). This study aims to find out how the pattern of patron clients in the election of the regional head in Lalingato Village, Tirawuta District, East Kolaka Regency in 2015. The research method used is a qualitative descriptive approach. The research data were collected using interview and documentation techniques while the data analysis techniques in this study consisted of data reduction, presentation of data, and giving conclusions. The results show that the pattern of the client patron will occur if there is a personal interest in it, where the patron here provides assistance, benefits, and protection to the client, which then the client reciprocates by providing general support and personal services to patrons. H. Tony Herbiyansyah's victory in the 2015 East Kolaka election in Lalingato Village was due to the dominant role of the patron in the village with the patron-client working as a support system that led to reciprocal relationships, even though other couples applied the same pattern, but the power of influence or into the pattern the patrons of other couples' clients are not as strong or deep as that of H. Tony Herbiyansyah.

Keywords: Client Patron, Regional Head Election, East Kolaka.

Collaborate Governance in Management PT. Mulia Jas in North Luwu District

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This Management Research aims to determine the Process of Collaborative Governance in Factory Waste PT. Jas Mulia. This type of research uses qualitative descriptive, data collection techniques are carried out through interview observations and a phenomenological approach that is directly related which describes the facts in the field, the number of informants is 3. The results showed that the stages of Collaborative Governance in the Waste Management of PT. Jas Mulia, namely, the existence of face-to-face dialogue between stakeholders that is multi-directional communication that is carried out once in six months to build trust shows that stakeholders who are directly involved in collaborative governance build mutual feelings when starting to build face. Commitment to show that stakeholders regard that commitment as a form of loyalty, commitment and responsibility in their goals. Sharing understanding between PT.Jas Mulia, and the community is carried out by sharing knowledge and information to complement each other's shortcomings with other parties. share understanding directly or indirectly.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance, Waste Management

Implementation of "Gammarana Manggala" Program in Tackling The Smell of Landfill Waste in Manggala Subdistrict, Makassar City

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The purpose of this research is to find out the implementation of the program "Gammarana Manggala" in tackling the smell of landfill waste in the District Manggala Makassar City. The type of research used is qualitative which is a form of research that aims to provide an overview as data collected from the objective field and get the results that the implementation of the program "Gammarana Manggala" can reduce the unpleasant odor caused by landfills (landfills) even though the results are not yet maximized in Tamangapa Village and Biring Romang Village because the area is a close area of landfill existence. However, still planting fragrant tree seedlings such as cambodia, white roses, lavender, jasmine, fragrant pandanus, and delicious night in 8 villages in Manggala Subdistrict.

Keywords: Policy Implementation, Waste Management, TPA Impact

The Art of Evaluating the Performance of Parliamentary Committees

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Assessing committees' performance has preoccupied literature on parliamentary committees for the past two decades. As a result, various evaluation methods have been devised to that effect. They include assessing committees' performance by measuring the number of important bills that committees pass, the number of important issues that committees address and the number of unimportant bills that committees blocks. While all these methods are important in advancing the knowledge on assessing committees' performance, they are not very useful to parliamentary actors such as parliamentarians as they lack the sense of contemporaneousness in their measurements. It is in this context that this paper innovatively presents a rule of thumb that suggests committees' performance should instantaneously be measured by the extent to which actions of a particular committee are consistent with three Es namely, *Economy, Effectiveness and Efficiency*.

Key Words: Committees, performances, economy, effectiveness and efficiency

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The Influence of Income Improvement Allowance Policy on Work Spirit of The Apparatus

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This study aims to describe and explain the effect of income improvement allowance policies on morale at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Bantaeng Regency. This research is a collaborative research (Mix method Research) for quantitative research. The sample in this study were 35 people with sampling technique using saturated sampling. As for qualitative research, using purposive sampling, the research subjects were 5 people. The results showed that the analysis of the income improvement allowance policy was in the very good category and the morale was in the good category. Based on the results of a simple linear regression test, it shows that the income improvement allowance policy variable has an effect of 56% on work morale at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Bantaeng Regency. From the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that the higher the provision of income improvement allowances, the higher the morale of the apparatus.

Keywords: Influence, income improvement allowance policy, morale

The Influence of Seagull Leadership on Employee Performance (Study at The Sub-District Office of Gantarang Sub-District, Paenre Lompoe Village Bulukumba Regency

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The Camat leadership in improving employee performance shows that in this case it shows how the Camat is leading the way, applying situational leadership theory more and combining it with a democratic type of leadership. Leadership is an ability or strength within a person to influence others in terms of work, in order to achieve a predetermined organizational target. The purpose of this study was to determine how much influence the Camat leadership had on employee performance at the Gantarang sub-district office, Paenre Lompoe village, Bulukumba district. The type of research used in this study is a type of quantitative research using data collection techniques used are questionnaires, observations, and documentation. Thus, this study describes how the influence of the sub-district leadership on employee performance and the factors that constrain the sub-district leadership in improving employee performance at the Gantarang District Head Office, Paenre Lompoe Village, Bulukumba Regency. Based on the findings in the field that the leadership of the Camat of Gantarang Sub-district, Paenre Lompoe Village, Bulukumba Regency, still lacks coordination with his subordinates, as if the sub-district head has official duties outside the office, his employees do not know about the Camat's return to the office so that if people come to meet the Camat are often disappointed because they are not in place, as well as improving the quality of performance of employees needs to be improved.

Keywords: Leadership, Employee Performance, District Office.

Gender Equality in The Placement of Structural Positions in Bone Regency, South Sulawesi

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Bureaucracy as a description of the government model in Indonesia is certainly much influenced by various elements, such as the demands of bureaucratic reform as a positive change step in order to realize the implementation of good public services for the community. In this context it does not despite the public's attention how it still pays attention to "gender" in its implementation. As is known that gender issues are also attached to various studies, no exception to the bureaucratic space. Internal Position A government organization in the center and in the area has a goal, namely providing services to the community and running a government activity program that has been arranged for the welfare of the community. In the realm of public life, especially political positions - strategic, the condition is not much different. The peak of attention to women's participation in the political sector appears from the trial of a 30% quota demand for women's candidates for legislative seats. These demands then get their formalities with Article 65 of Law No. 12/2003 concerning Elections. Many women who are not ready and supportive when fellow women advance competing in a political realm. So that it can be concluded that women and politics in the perspective of gender equality must be balanced and balanced without forgetting the essence and nature of gender equality is a very complicated concept and contains controversy. Structural position is a position that shows the duties, responsibilities, authority, and privileges of a civil servant to lead a state organization unit. Local Regulation No.3 of 2010 concerning Structural Position mentioned the requirement that the placement of Echelon II structure through the fit and proper test. With those who have regulations, women and men have the same opportunity and opportunity. But women still occupy a fewer department head positions

Keywords: Gender Equality, Structural Position

The Context of Global Problems towards Sustainable Development of Society and Higher Education and Science

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This research will contribute to the effective implementation of higher education development strategy under the conditions of globalization and internationalization in the context of sustainable development of society. This is due to the integration of higher education of Ukraine into the European Higher Education Area and the European Research Area; the necessity to study the compliance of strategic guidelines of higher education and its specific educational models with the needs of civilizational progress towards a sustainable future, peace, mutual understanding, mutual respect and care for the environment (reflected through the concepts of information society, knowledge society, sustainable development, globalization, internationalization of higher education, culture of peace, global citizenship, etc.). The implementation of research results will ensure increasing the level and quality of higher education internationalization in Ukraine, shaping a worldview background to stimulate and ensure sustainable development of society, increasing social responsibility of higher education and strengthening its function of serving society.

Keywords: Globalization, Sustainable Development, Internationalization, Higher Education, Social Activism.

Presentation Schedule

“Priming Governance For Global Political Dynamics Through Collaborative Governance and Public Policy”

24 JULY, 2021

ROOM : 1
 MODERATOR : Nur Muliasari MS
 CO-HOST : Muhammad Jaya Rifaldi
 THE JUDGES : Nurkhaerah, S.IP, M.IP
 TIME : 11-00-12.30 WITA

NO.	NAME	TITLE	AFFILIATION
1.	Abdul Mushawwir ¹ , Mohamad Amin ² , Saifullah ³	ALTERNATIVE EDUCATION SERVICES FOR PAPUA NATIVES (OAP) IN WEST PAPUA PROVINCE IN 2021	Magister Ilmu administrasi Publik
2.	Anugerah Paradana S. Marsuki ¹ , Irwanto AR ² , Nur Resky Amalia B ³	GOVERNMENT POLICY IN IMPLEMENTING EDUCATION THROUGH ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID-19	Magister Ilmu administrasi Publik
3.	Rusdi ¹ , Farhan Adi Saputra ² , Nuryanti Mustari ³	IMPLEMENTATION OF ELECTRONIC MONEY (E-MONEY) POLICY AT THE TOLLGATE REFORM OF MAKASSAR CITY	Magister Ilmu administrasi Publik
4.	Ahwal Gunawan Rasyid ¹ , Nuryanti Mustari ² , Syamsul Bahri ³ , Hasbullah ⁴	GOVERNMENT POLICY IN IMPLEMENTING RESTRICTIONS ON COMMUNITY ACTIVITIES TO CONTROL THE SPREAD OF COVID-19 IN THE CITY OF MAKASSAR.	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
5.	Nurhalisa ¹ , Muh. Rizal ² , Baso Hasrullah ³ , Maghfira Azzyahra ⁴	ANALYSIS OF THE REPRESENTATIVE FUNCTIONS OF THE VILLAGE CONSULTATIVE AGENCY IN DEMOCRATIZING VILLAGE GOVERNMENT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
6.	Nuryanti Mustari ¹ , Nur Iftitah ² , Lukman Nul Hakim Amran Saputra ³ , Cahyani Putri Mondo ⁴	THE INFLUENCE OF INCOME IMPROVEMENT ALLOWANCE POLICY ON WORK SPIRIT OF THE APPARATUS	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar

7.	Sherly Yulianti ¹ , Asraf Bayu Saputra ² , Muslimin Aditya Saputra Mustari ³ , Muh Ichzan Syaiful ⁴	POLICY EVALUATION OF PERDA NUMBER 11 YEAR 2012 CONCERNING RURAL AND URBAN LAND AND BUILDING TAX	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
8.	A.Rezki Tenri Ulung ¹ , Andi Andriadi ² , Wahyu Muhammad Nento ³ , Ariyandi ⁴	"ROLE OF BAPPEDA IN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT TO KNOW THE IMPLEMENTATION OF TASKS AND FUNCTIONS IN GORONTALO"	Universitas muhammadiyah makassar
9..	Muhammad Taaruf Aris ¹ , Ahmad Azhar Mawardi ² , Tipani Chaminra ³	EFFECT OF ONLINE LEARNING POLICY IN THE ERA OF COVID-19 ON THE QUALITY OF STUDENTS OF STATE 8 SMALL BULUKUMBA IN BULUKUMBA DISTRICT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
10.	Dina Firdaus ¹ , Andi Rahmat Nizar Hidayat ² , Almaidah Usman ³	DISPARITY OF CENTRAL AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT POLICIES IN TACKLING THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE PEOPLE OF MAKASSAR CITY	Universitas Muhammadiya Makassar
11.	Viktor Zinchenko ¹ , Mariia Debych ² , Oksana Bulvinska ³ , Viktoriiia Vorona ⁴	THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL PROBLEMS TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY AND HIGHER EDUCATION AND SCIENCE	Institute of Higher Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine

Presentation Schedule

“Priming Governance For Global Political Dynamics Through Collaborative Governance and Public Policy”

24 JULY, 2021

ROOM : 2
 MODERATOR : Nurul Rahmi Aulia
 CO-HOST : Vinka Adrina Sahrir
 THE JUDGES : Ahmad Harakan, S.IP, M.HI
 TIME : 11-00-12.30 WITA

NO.	NAME	TITTLE	AFFILIATION
1.	Hasan Basri ¹ , Nuryanti Mustari ² , Asriadi Ali ³ , Ansyari Wijaya ⁴	DISASTER MANAGEMENT CONCEPTS BASED ON PUBLIC POLICY PERSPECTIVE	Magister Ilmu administrasi Publik
2.	Faidzul Abror Mustafa ¹ , Anto K ² , La Ode Andi Armada ³ , La Ode Mardan Sakti Putra Rustama ⁴	IMPLEMENTATION THE KENDARI REGIONAL DISASTER MANAGEMENT AGENCY (BPBD) FUNCTION IN FLOOD DISASTER MANAGEMENT ON THE WANGGU RIVER KENDARI CITY	Kota Kendari
3.	Fera Juliana Fajar ¹ , Riski Amaliyah ² , Arif Rahman Setiawan ³ , Muh Rasyidi Mahmud ⁴	TOWARDS IMPROVED FLOOD DISASTER GOVERNANCE IN LUWU UTARA (PARTNERSHIP OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECTOR)	Magister Ilmu administrasi Publik
4.	Muh Hasbi Azis Agani ¹ , Ahmad Takbir Abadi ² , Dwi Nur Ilma Aulia ³ , Herman ⁴	LOCAL GOVERNMENT STRATEGIES IN MANAGING FLOOD DISASTER IN TOMPOBULU DISTRICT, MAROS REGENCY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia
5.	Annisa Almaulidia Rukka ¹ , Alwi Iswar ² , Ahmiranil Khaerat ³ , Amir Muhiddin ⁴	IMPLEMENTATION OF BRIGADE POLICY FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE FOR NATURAL DISASTER RESPONSE IN BANTAENG REGENCY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia
6.	Adila Puspa Hestiantini ¹ , Nursaleh hartaman ² , Sarmito ³	WOMEN’S POLITICAL COMMUNICATION (DR. KAROLIN’S COMMUNICATION ON SOCIAL MEDIA)	Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta

7.	Andi Visca Irfa Nyssa ¹ , Muh. Iksan ² , Yuliana ³ , Nurfitri Alfiah S ⁴	THE EXISTENCE OF TODAY'S WOMEN IN THE ORGANIZING OF ELECTIONS IN MAKASSAR CITY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
8.	Muh Nasir ¹ , Muhammad Fiqriansyah Tahir ² , Nurul Izzah ³ , Andi Eby Kumarul ⁴	KESETARAAN GENDER DALAM PENEMPATAN JABATAN DI KABUPATEN BONE	Universitas muhammadiyah makassar
9.	Jumria K ¹ , Nurul Fitriana Harsyaf ² , Rizqi Jannatun Naim ³ , Iqbal Nur Arfah ⁴	INVOLVEMENT OF WOMEN IN POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT	Universitas muhammadiyah makassar
10.	Sri Wahyuni ¹ , Julianita ² , Risma Khaerati ³	WOMEN AND POLITICS IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF FEMINISM AND GENDER EQUALITY IN INDONESIA: A CASE IN MAKASSAR	Government Science
11.	Y. Pinchuk ¹ , I. Oleksyn ² , O. Popova ³ , N. Sokolova ⁴	THE ROLE OF MODERN CONCEPTS OF SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATION IN THE INSTUTIONAL PROVISION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES	Department of Social Sciences and Humanities of the National University of Ukraine on Physical Education and Sport

Presentation Schedule

“Priming Governance For Global Political Dynamics Through Collaborative Governance and Public Policy”

24 JULY, 2021

ROOM : 3
 MODERATOR : Shinta Alfiah Nur
 CO-HOST : Andi Nur Faizah
 THE JUDGES : Nursaleh Hartaman, S.IP, M.IP
 TIME : 13-00-14.30 WITA

NO.	NAME	TITLE	AFFILIATION
1.	Sitti Atirah H Surullah ¹ , Ilham Nur Pratama ² , Alfira Putri Rengganis ³ , Revalina ⁴	IMPLEMENTATION OF "GAMMARANA MANGGALA" PROGRAM IN TACKLING THE SMELL OF LANDFILL WASTE IN MANGGALA SUBDISTRICT, MAKASSAR CITY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
2.	Hilaliah ¹ , Sartika ² , Nur Anzari Amin ³ , Drs. H. Ansyari Mone dan Rudi Hardi ⁴	SMART GOVERNANCE PROGRAM JENEPONTO GAMMARA AS A CITY BRAND IN JENEPONTO DISTRICT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
3.	Abel Kinyondo ¹	THE ART OF EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF PARLIAMENTARY COMMITTEES	University dar es salaam Tanzania
4.	Faidzul Abror Mustafa ¹ , La Ode Andi Armada ² , La Ode Mardan Sakti Putra Rustaman ³ , La Ode Muhammad Rifaldi ⁴	CLIENT PATRON PATTERN OF EAST KOLAKA REGIONAL HEAD OF ELECTION 2015 (CASE IN LALINGATO VILLAGE, TIRAWUTA DISTRICT, EAST KOLAKA)	Kendari City
5.	Muhammad Habibi ¹	THE PANDEMIC AND THE DECLINE OF INDONESIAN DEMOCRACY: THE SNARE OF PATRONAGE AND CLIENTELISM OF LOCAL DEMOCRACY	Pusat Penelitian Pengembangan Pendidikan dan Pelatihan: Badan Pengawas Pemilihan Umum Republik Indonesia
6.	Alya Husain ¹ ,	COLLABORATE GOVERNANCE IN	Universitas

	Wahyuni ² , Kartina ³ , Hardianto Hawing ⁴	MANAGEMENT PT. MULIA JAS IN NORTH LUWU DISTRICT	Muhammadiyah Makassar
7.	Siti Wahida ¹ , Nurjannah ² , Emmang Arfa Wijaya Darwis ³ , Muh. Wais Alqarnain ⁴	THE EFFECT OF VILLAGE EXPANTION ON PUBLIC DEVELOPMENT AND SERVICES IN WONOREJO TIMUR VILLAGE, MANGKUTANA DISTRICT, LUWU TIMUR REGENCY	Government Science, Social Science and Political Science, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
8.	Rahmad Nur ¹ , Isra Rezky Utami ² , Israfanah Salam ³	COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF HORTICULTURAL AGRICULTURE SECTOR IN RUMBIA SUBDISTRICT JENEPONTO DISTRICT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
9.	Dian Ekawati ¹ , Nurwanda ² , Nurfadillah ³ , Hasanuddin ⁴	ROLE VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING VILLAGE OWNED ENTERPRISES (BUMDES) IN BONTORAPPO VILLAGE TAROWANG SUBDISTRICT JENEPONTO	Government Sciences, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Muhammadiyah University of Makassar, Makassar, Indonesia, 90221.
10.	Nurlathifah Raqibah ¹ , Chaerul Mahdi ² , Nadia Sukmawati ³ , Fitriani Sari Handayani ⁴	GOVERNMENT INNOVATION IN EGGPLANT MARKET MANAGEMENT AMID COVID 19 PANDEMIC IN MAKASSAR CITY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
11.	Ahmad Muqtasir Muqsit ¹ , Marwan ² , Muh. Khalifah P.Hw ³ , Risman ⁴	INTERNAL YOUTH, SPORTS AND TOURISM DEPARTMENT STRATEGIES DEVELOPING LEWAJA NATURAL BATH TOURISM OBJECTS IN ENREKANG DISTRICT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar

Presentation Schedule

“Priming Governance For Global Political Dynamics Through Collaborative Governance and Public Policy”

24 JULY, 2021

ROOM : 4
 MODERATOR : Ilham Nur Pratama Rahman
 CO-HOST : Alfina
 THE JUDGES : Herman S.Pd, M.Pd
 TIME : 13-00-14.30 WITA

NO.	NAME	TITLE	AFFILIATION
1.	Lesia Chervona ¹ , Natalia Lakusha ² , Nataliia Fialko ³ , Olha Palamarchuk ⁴	SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES OF THE EDUCATION AND SCIENCE SYSTEM AS AN INTEGRATIVE COMPONENT OF THE GLOBAL COOPERATION STRATEGY	Department Interaction between Universities and Society, Institute of Higher Education, National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine
2.	Iis Suedi ¹ , Sry Resky Humuyani ² , Mushlihah Muhayyang ³ , Nursaleh ⁴	IMPLEMENTATION OF GOOD ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE IN WATERFRONT CITY DEVELOPMENT IN MAJENE DISTRICT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
3.	Anna Wardana ¹ , Siti Nurhaliza Febryna Khaidir ² , Fitrah Awalia Salam ³ , Ainia Dzikra Putri Isnaad ⁴	GOOD TOURISM GOVERNANCE OF THE MANAGEMENT "BEAUTIFUL MALINO" IN GOWA REGENCY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
4.	Andi Wiwiek Fhatima Azzahra ¹ , Muhammad Shaiful Nur ² , Muhammad Yusril Syarief ³ , Figri Al- Ghifary ⁴	THE INFLUENCE OF SEAHULL LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE (STUDY AT THE SUB-DISTRICT OFFICE OF GANTARANG SUB-DISTRICT, PAENRE LOMPOE VILLAGE BULUKUMBA REGENCY	Governmental Sciences, Social and Political Sciences, Bulukumba, Indonesia, 90221
5.	Achmad Fadhil ¹ , Ahmad Mutawakkal ² , Risal Tanjung ³ , Wisdam Nofanda Gunawan ⁴	THE INFLU OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE SCOPE OF GOVERNMENT IN THE OFFICE SAMATA SOMBAOPU DISTRICT, GOWA REGENCY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar

6.	Ahmad Midrar ¹ , Muh. Irfan Aryabi Mamal ² , Elsa Purwaningsih ³ , Ade Nurfianti ⁴	HELPING COMMUNITIES FACING SOCIAL CHANGES AS IMPACT OF COVID 19	
7.	Hasrul Nur ¹ , Ulfa Dwiyantri ² , Sukmawati ³ , Andi Padamani ⁴	PUBLIC POLICY COMMUNICATION IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF HEALTH PROTOCOLS AT PKL GOR SUDIANG IN MAKASSAR CITY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
8.	Ulfiah Syukri ¹ , Mayang Sari ² , Zul Jalali Wal Ikram ³ , Muh. Jalil ⁴	GOVERNANCE LAND OWNERSHIP IN MAKASSAR CITY: AN ANALYSIS OF THE POLITICAL STRUGGLE OF THE URBAN POOR IN BARABARAYYA MAKASSAR CITY	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
9.	Marzuki Mansyur ¹ , Fildayani ² , Muh. Imran ³	STRATEGIES AND POLICIES IN ACCELERATION OF COMPLETE SYSTEMIC LAND REGISTRATION (PTSL) IN 2021 IN THE DISTRICT OF SELAYAR	Magister ilmu administrasi publik
10.	Nurul Wahdaniyah ¹ , Elviana ² , Muja'didatunisa ³	EVALUATION OF COVID-19 HANDLING POLICY IMPLEMENTATION IN GOWA DISTRICT	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar
11.	Ksatriawan Zaenuddin ¹ , Muh. Ilham ² , Amar ³ , Novhita Dewi Anggariksa Putri ⁴	RESILIENCE OF HAMLET-BASED SMES IN BANTAENG REGENCY DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC	Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar

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